

A Causal Relationship Model of Factors Affecting High Performance Organizations of Schools under the Primary Educational Service Area Offices in the Northeast

Sukanya Phomarak

Doctor of Philosophy in Division of Educational Administration and Development,
Faculty of Education, Sakon Nakhon Rajabhat University, Thailand

Waro Phengsawat

Lecturer in Division of Educational Administration and Development,
Faculty of Education, Sakon Nakhon Rajabhat University, Thailand

Akkaluck Pheasa

Lecturer in Division of Educational Administration and Development,
Faculty of Education, Sakon Nakhon Rajabhat University, Thailand

ABSTRACT: This research aims to study; 1) the components of high-performance organizations in schools and the factors affecting such organizations, 2) the development and validation of a causal relationship model of factors affecting high-performance organizations in schools, and 3) the guidelines for developing high-performance organizations in schools under the jurisdiction of the Primary Educational Service Area Offices in the Northeastern region. The research was conducted in three phases: Phase 1: Studying the components and factors affecting high-performance organizations in schools by reviewing relevant theoretical concepts, documents, and research. Experts were interviewed (5 individuals), and the appropriateness and feasibility were evaluated by 5 experts. Phase 2: Developing and validate the model's consistency with empirical data. The sample group consisted of 597 school administrators and teachers selected through multi-stage sampling. The data were collected using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire, with the discrimination power ranging from .28 to .93 and reliability of .97. The frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were analyzed, along with Pearson correlation coefficients and structural equation modeling using software. Phase 3: Showing guidelines for developing high-performance organizations in schools were formulated based on the results of Phase 2 and evaluated for appropriateness, feasibility, and utility by 5 experts.

The research findings revealed that:

1. The components of high-performance organizations in schools consist of six elements; focus on personnel quality, focus on service recipients and stakeholders, organizational leadership, strategic management, organizational culture, and organizational innovation. Overall, these components were found to be highly appropriate and feasible. The factors influencing high-performance organizations in schools include five factors; transformational leadership, human resource management, learning organization, total quality management, and competence of organizational members. These factors were also found to be highly appropriate and feasible.

2. The developed model was consistent with the empirical data, with values of Chi-square = 340.40, df = 309, p-value = 0.10, $\chi^2/df = 1.10$, RMSEA = 0.01, GFI = 0.96, AGFI = 0.95. The status of being a high-performance organization in schools was directly influenced by the transformational leadership variable and indirectly influenced by the same variable through the learning organization and organizational members' competence variables. The variables in the model explained 95% of the variance in being a high-performance organization.

3. The guidelines for transformational leadership affecting the development of high-performance organizations included five objectives, five strategies, 53 implementation methods, and 13 success indicators. These were found to be highly appropriate, feasible, and beneficial.

Keywords: Causal Relationship Model, High-performance Organizations in Schools, Factors

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1. Introduction

An organization that strives for excellence or a High Performance Organization (HPO) is an approach to organizational management with a new work structure that focuses on excellence. It emphasizes valuable and quality services, prioritizes learning and innovation, and fosters an environment where personnel can exchange knowledge. It also enhances the ability to adapt to changing environments while attempting to reduce bureaucracy to enable faster management processes. Additionally, it ensures that the organization can align its operations with its strategies or vision to achieve its set goals. For a public organization to transform itself into a high-performance organization and adapt to the constantly changing external environment—whether economic, social, political, or technological—the organization's leaders or managers must have a strong desire to develop their organization to be adaptive and capable of survival in a continually changing environment. Therefore, in transforming an organization into a high-performance organization, the management and personnel are crucial factors that serve as indicators of success and the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization (Tatiya Panomwan Na Ayuthaya, 2017).

The development of an organization to possess high capabilities is essential for every organization to adapt to the modern world to meet the needs of service recipients who demand speed, quality, and an organization with contingency plans for various situations that could impact operations from all sides. This aligns with Thipawan Losuwannaratt (2016), who stated that the importance and necessity of developing a high-performance organization lie in gaining a sustainable competitive advantage. It involves having better long-term organizational performance than other similar organizations. For an organization to outperform others, it is necessary to continuously improve its performance or capabilities by producing quality goods or services. Organizations that cannot develop themselves in this way inevitably lose their competitive advantage. The current social and environmental problems, both domestically and internationally, are changing at a faster pace than before. A high-performance school organization is one that succeeds in managing teaching and learning, contributes to students' growth, prepares them for further education and career readiness, and maintains high expectations for success in education. It continues to succeed and maintain excellence while having a clear mission, continually improving its work systems, formulating strategies, and implementing plans aligned with its vision and mission. The school undergoes holistic development, competes at various levels, and continuously strives for academic excellence, with active participation from service recipients and stakeholders, ensuring the sustainable success of the school (Thanwa

Watitpan, 2021). The key to becoming a high-performance school includes designing organizational work processes, having a flexible and adaptable organizational structure that responds to changes, decentralizing work responsibilities, connecting various parts of the organization through integrated work systems, and ensuring that personnel possess the necessary knowledge and skills for effective operations.

The 21st century is a world where information can be accessed rapidly, and people are more aware of and responsive to changes. As a result, the public has gained greater knowledge and understanding and is more willing to participate in educational management. Meanwhile, the structure and system of education are still managed under traditional rules, regulations, and operational plans. This has led to issues of inefficiency in management and the development of educational quality. Reforming the administrative structure of central, regional, and school-level agencies, along with addressing and improving the personnel management system for administrators, teachers, and educational personnel, is necessary to resolve these issues. This would enable educational institutions to manage and deliver education that is accountable for quality standards to learners more efficiently and effectively (Office of the Education Council Secretariat, 2017). The effective management of school affairs is crucial in translating educational policies into practice to achieve the specified objectives or goals. This depends on the school's management process. When examining the current operations based on the roles and responsibilities defined by the Ministry of Education, it is evident that educational institutions are currently unable to achieve the desired outcomes. Furthermore, they cannot effectively implement policies to achieve significant results. The efforts to reform education, aimed at raising the quality of schools, have only been partially successful. Most educational institutions still experience delays, which has led to Thailand's low competitiveness in education compared to other countries. This also extends to the fields of science and technology, where Thailand ranks poorly. According to the 2022 IMD World Competitiveness Ranking, Thailand ranked 33rd, a drop of 5 places from the previous year when it ranked 28th in 2021. This decline highlights the need for development in several areas, particularly in health, environment, and education, where Thailand ranked 2nd and 1st lowest, respectively (National Science and Technology Development Agency (NSTDA), 2023).

Primary schools under the Office of the Basic Education Commission in the Northeastern region face several challenges according to the analysis of development conditions for strategic planning. Many schools are small, leading to issues such as resource shortages and insufficient teachers across all grades. Some teachers are teaching subjects outside their qualifications, and students' national test scores (O-NET, RT, NT, V-NET, N-NET, B-NET) are below the national average. There is also a lack of management systems for learning resources, and educational databases are not well-connected between agencies and are outdated (Office of Education Region 10, 2023). To address these challenges, the approach to educational development involves supporting schools in managing quality education independently and effectively within the framework set by the Ministry of Education. This includes establishing committees to drive the integration of education management at regional, provincial group, and provincial levels, fostering participatory educational development across all sectors. It also aims to create and develop networks for cooperation in education management among relevant agencies and promote

the shared use of resources (Office of Education Region 13, 2022). Thus, enhancing the efficiency of each school is crucial. The transition to becoming a high-performance organization in schools is a strategic factor that creates a competitive advantage. When schools change their operational processes by leveraging new ideas and creating educational innovations, it directly benefits the school by enhancing its competitive edge and improving overall school efficiency.

For these reasons and the significance mentioned above, the researcher is interested in conducting a study on the causal relationship model of factors influencing high-performance organizations in schools under the jurisdiction of the Primary Educational Service Area Offices in the Northeastern region. The purpose is to identify the factors that impact the performance of these schools. The findings from this research can serve as a guideline and be beneficial in developing a framework for school management under the Office of the Basic Education Commission in the future.

Research Framework

This research study examines the causal relationship model of factors influencing high-performance organizations in schools under the Office of the Basic Education Commission in the Northeastern region. The study involved reviewing relevant literature and previous research on factors influencing high-performance organizations in schools, including works by; Pawalin Posayannon (2014), Thararath Phusak (2015), Nantawan Boonchouy (2016), Supansa Sesangsri (2016), Nisara Hongsa (2017), Natchanuch Sudchadee (2018), and Thida Apiromprueksa (2018), Natthasaran Mangklanakhesuan (2019), Ratchanee Sittidumrong (2019), Surasak Chamarum (2019), Watcharapol Phophoonsak (2020), Sunisa Thipat (2020), Orphin Boonsin (2020), Mayuree Panthachoti (2021), Warunee Phumisrikaew (2021), Jesdaporn Phutpa (2022), Prasit Thananan (2023), Yuree Khamphirom (2023), and Rintarapatsak Chaiwattana (2023) as illustrated in Figure 1

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework for Research on the Causal Relationship Model of Factors Influencing High-Performance Organizations in Schools under the Primary Educational Service Area Offices in the Northeastern Region

Research Objectives

1. To study the components of high-performance schools and the factors affecting high-performance schools.
2. To develop and verify a causal relationship model of factors affecting high-performance schools under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast region with empirical data.
3. To explore the approaches for developing high-performance schools under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast region.

Background

The attainment of higher education is commonly considered a significant component in determining individual and societal advancement. It functions as a crucial tool for accessing possibilities to improve one's social status, achieve economic security, and foster personal growth. Nevertheless, the process of acquiring a higher education degree is frequently filled with obstacles that can have a substantial impact on student achievements. Family support is a crucial aspect that significantly impacts educational achievement. Family support, which includes emotional, financial, and intellectual aid, is essential in influencing a student's capacity to negotiate the intricacies of higher education. This study investigates the varying levels of familial assistance among several socioeconomic groups and its influence on higher education achievement.

Numerous studies have extensively demonstrated the importance of familial support in achieving educational success. Academic researchers have continuously emphasized the significance of a nurturing family environment in promoting academic motivation, resilience, and a feeling of inclusion among students (Alfaro et al., 2020). Family support can be demonstrated in various ways, such as providing financial assistance, offering emotional support, and actively participating in academic activities like helping with homework or attending school events. Nevertheless, the level and characteristics of this assistance frequently vary widely among various socioeconomic groups, resulting in discrepancies in educational achievements.

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a crucial factor that influences both the educational opportunities available to individuals and the achievements they achieve. According to Sirin (2021), it has an impact on the accessibility of resources, the quality of educational institutions, and the overall social context in which a student works. Families with higher socioeconomic status typically have more financial means, which enables them to offer their children superior educational materials, private tutoring, and other sorts of academic enrichment. In addition, these families may possess a greater amount of time and energy to actively participate in their children's education, creating a more supportive and favorable learning environment. Conversely, families with lower socioeconomic status may encounter difficulties in offering equivalent assistance due to financial limitations, rigorous employment timetables, and restricted availability of educational resources.

When correlation between familial assistance and the achievement of higher education gets increasingly intricate when taking into account the convergence of socioeconomic position and cultural influences. Family perceptions and involvement in schooling can be greatly influenced by cultural norms and expectations. For instance, several cultures place significant importance on the collective success of the family, perceiving the accomplishments of one family member as indicative of the honor and social standing of the entire family (González et al., 2019). Under such circumstances, families are more inclined to allocate resources towards their children's education, even if it involves substantial personal or financial hardship. In contrast, certain cultural contexts may prioritize urgent economic survival over long-term educational objectives, leading to a reduced focus on formal education.

This study aims to investigate the diverse and complex impact of family support on achieving higher education by conducting a comparative analysis across various socioeconomic backgrounds. This research, being qualitative in nature, enables a thorough exploration of the actual experiences of students and their families. It offers vital insights into how family dynamics impact educational achievements. By gathering their perspectives, this study seeks to illuminate the obstacles and possibilities that influence the educational paths of students from various socioeconomic backgrounds.

An examination of the current body of research indicates that students from wealthier socioeconomic backgrounds are more prone to receiving significant financial assistance from their families. This assistance can help alleviate the financial strain of tuition fees, housing expenses, and other costs associated with pursuing higher education (Fosnacht & Dong, 2020). This financial assistance frequently goes beyond covering the direct expenses

of school and includes a wider range of features, such as providing access to technology, study materials, and extracurricular activities that enhance the entire educational experience. Furthermore, families with a higher socioeconomic status (SES) are frequently more capable of offering guidance and mentorship, utilizing their own educational backgrounds and networks to assist their children in achieving their academic and professional goals.

Conversely, students belonging to poorer socioeconomic backgrounds may encounter substantial financial obstacles that hinder their ability to pursue higher education. The exorbitant fees associated with tuition, books, and living costs sometimes act as a barrier, prompting numerous students to seek part-time employment or depend on student loans to fund their education (Perna, 2021). The financial burdens might generate extra strain and restrict the amount of time and effort that students can allocate to their academic pursuits. In addition, the limited availability of financial resources may hinder students' ability to receive crucial academic support services, such as tutoring or counseling, which are vital for achieving academic success.

The emotional and psychological dimensions of familial support play an equally significant role in influencing educational achievements. A nurturing familial atmosphere can offer students the necessary support and drive to persist through the difficulties encountered in pursuing higher education (Wang & Heppner, 2020). When families encourage education and show confidence in their children's talents, it can help them develop a strong belief in them

themselves and a strong will to succeed academically. These factors are important indicators of academic achievement. In addition, receiving emotional support from family members helps alleviate the stress and anxiety commonly linked to the pressures of higher education, enhancing mental health and overall well-being.

Socioeconomic conditions also impact the capacity of families to provide emotional assistance. Families facing financial difficulties or other stressors may find it challenging to provide the same level of emotional support, as they may prioritize meeting essential requirements or tackling other challenges (Conger et al., 2021). Under such circumstances, students may experience a sense of seclusion or being overburdened without the support and motivation that could assist them in successfully managing the challenges of tertiary education. Understanding the wider social and economic circumstances in which family assistance functions is critical, as these factors can greatly influence the quality and effectiveness of the help offered.

Family engagement in educational activities and communication with educational institutions is a crucial aspect in achieving higher education. Studies indicate that parental engagement in education is linked to elevated academic performance, improved school attendance, and a heightened probability of pursuing further education (Hill & Tyson, 2021). When families actively participate in their children's education by attending parent-teacher conferences or helping with homework, they can strengthen the importance of education and promote academic achievement. Nevertheless, the extent of parental participation frequently differs according to socioeconomic class, with families from higher SES

backgrounds being more inclined to partake in these endeavors as a result of increased availability of information, resources, and leisure time.

In contrast, families with lower socioeconomic status may encounter obstacles to participation, such as linguistic hurdles, limited knowledge of the school system, or conflicting obligations (Cooper & Crosnoe, 2020). These obstacles can restrict their capacity to successfully assist their children in their education, perhaps resulting in lower academic performance and a decreased likelihood of achieving higher education. This emphasizes the necessity for educational institutions to acknowledge and tackle the many difficulties encountered by families from all socioeconomic backgrounds, promoting more comprehensive and encouraging environments for all kids.

Ultimately, the influence of familial assistance on achieving higher education is an intricate and diverse matter, intricately connected to socioeconomic elements. This study aims to investigate the diverse aspects of family support among individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds, analyzing the impact of financial, emotional, and academic support on students' educational achievements. This project seeks to use a qualitative approach to understand and document the detailed experiences of students and their families. By doing so, it attempts to gain useful insights into how family dynamics influence higher education achievement. The results of this study have significant consequences for educational policies and practices, emphasizing the necessity for focused interventions that cater to the varied requirements of kids and their families, especially those from disadvantaged socioeconomic situations.

Problem Statement

Despite the widespread recognition of higher education as a critical tool for achieving upward social mobility and financial security, significant disparities in educational attainment persist across various socioeconomic classes. Family support, which includes financial, emotional, and intellectual aid, is crucial in determining a student's capacity to excel in higher education. Socioeconomic status (SES) frequently significantly impacts the accessibility and efficacy of this assistance. Students from higher socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds generally have advantages such as more financial resources, increased parental involvement, and better access to academic opportunities. Students from lower SES backgrounds, on the other hand, frequently encounter obstacles such as financial constraints, limited access to high-quality educational resources, and insufficient parental support due to socioeconomic pressures.

These inequalities contribute to an expanding disparity in academic performance, as children from underprivileged origins have a lower likelihood of attaining higher education, hence perpetuating cycles of poverty and restricting upward social mobility. Although previous studies have examined the overall influence of family support on academic achievements, there is a dearth of comprehensive comprehension regarding how these dynamics manifest in various socioeconomic settings and the particular obstacles encountered by students from lower socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds.

This study aims to fill this void by investigating the impact of family assistance on achieving higher education, specifically focusing on socioeconomic inequalities. The study

seeks to investigate the subjective experiences of students from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds in relation to various forms of family support and how these experiences impact their academic achievements. The findings will provide a vital understanding of the structural disparities that affect educational achievements and guide approaches to improving educational fairness and assistance for all students, irrespective of their socioeconomic situation.

The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of family support on attaining higher education, specifically by analyzing the disparities in financial, emotional, and academic support among students from different socioeconomic backgrounds and the potential effects of these differences on their academic achievements. The objective of the study is to examine the range and magnitude of family support offered to students from various socioeconomic backgrounds while they are pursuing higher education. Additionally, it seeks to assess the impact of financial, emotional, and intellectual support from family on their academic success, perseverance, and general welfare. Furthermore, this study aims to ascertain the obstacles faced by students from underprivileged socioeconomic backgrounds in obtaining sufficient family support and investigate the impact of these obstacles on their overall academic achievement.

To guide this investigation, the study asks the following questions: What differences exist in the type and amount of family support offered to students from various socioeconomic backgrounds? To what extent does the provision of financial, emotional, and academic assistance by family's impact students' academic achievements, retention rates, and overall welfare in higher education? What are the particular challenges faced by students from underprivileged socioeconomic backgrounds in obtaining family support, and how do these challenges affect their academic performance in undergraduate education?

2. Literature Review

The impact of familial support on higher education has received much scholarly attention because of its substantial influence on students' academic success. Family support has a crucial role in students' academic achievement, emotional well-being, and overall educational outcomes as they navigate the difficulties of higher education. This literature review analyzes the current studies on the influence of family support on achieving higher education, specifically exploring how this support differs based on socioeconomic backgrounds and the consequences for educational fairness.

The correlation between family support and higher education attainment

Family support comprises a range of aid, such as financial, emotional, and academic support, which all contribute to a student's capacity to excel in higher education. Studies widely recognize the significance of familial support in achieving educational success, emphasizing its role in fostering academic drive, resilience, and perseverance among students (Garcia & Weiss, 2019). People commonly regard family support as a protective barrier against the difficulties and pressures associated with higher education. It offers students the necessary resources and motivation to overcome hurdles and attain academic accomplishments.

Financial aid is crucial for families, especially when it comes to higher education, where the prices for tuition, textbooks, and living costs can be significant. Studies have demonstrated that students who receive financial assistance from their families have a higher probability of enrolling in and successfully completing higher education programs (Perna & Finney, 2019). This assistance can mitigate the economic strain on students, enabling them to concentrate on their academic pursuits without the additional stress of working extensive hours to meet their financial obligations. Furthermore, the provision of financial assistance by families can augment students' opportunities to utilize resources such as technology, study materials, and extracurricular activities, all of which contribute to a more enhanced educational experience (Fosnacht & Dong, 2020).

Family involvement in higher education. An atmosphere characterized by familial support can cultivate a feeling of inclusion and personal effectiveness in students, which are significant indicators of academic achievement (Wang & Heppner, 2020). Students who perceive their families to be committed to their education and have confidence in their potential to succeed are more inclined to persist in the face of the difficulties encountered in higher education. Receiving emotional support from family members helps alleviate the stress and anxiety commonly linked to academic pressures, hence enhancing mental health and overall well-being (Conger et al., 2021).

Academic help provided by the family is critical for achieving higher education, as well as financial and emotional assistance. This support can manifest in diverse ways, encompassing aid with homework, motivation to achieve academic objectives, and engagement in educational endeavors such as parent-teacher meetings (Hill & Tyson, 2021). When families actively participate in their children's education, they may reinforce the importance of learning and assist kids in cultivating the necessary skills and behaviors for academic success. Nevertheless, families' own educational experiences and knowledge of the higher education system frequently shape the extent of academic assistance they offer (Cooper & Crosnoe, 2020).

Socioeconomic status and family support.

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a crucial determinant of the type and level of family assistance in higher education. Families with better socioeconomic status generally own more significant financial means, allowing them to offer more substantial financial assistance to their children (Sirin, 2021). Furthermore, these families are more inclined to possess the necessary time and vitality to actively participate in their children's education, providing both scholastic support and emotional motivation. Consequently, students from higher socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds frequently have access to a more comprehensive support structure that enhances their achievement in higher education.

Conversely, families with lesser socioeconomic status may have substantial obstacles when it comes to offering assistance to their children in pursuing higher education. Financial limitations pose a major obstacle for these families, as they may face difficulties in affording tuition fees, purchasing textbooks, and meeting other educational obligations (Perna, 2021). Students from lower socioeconomic origins often experience financial challenges that can result in heightened stress levels and a higher probability of having to work while pursuing their studies. This, in turn, can negatively impact their

academic performance. Moreover, the constrained financial means of these families may impede students' ability to avail themselves of academic support services, such as tutoring or counseling, that have the potential to improve their educational achievements (Gaddis, 2019).

Socioeconomic issues also impact the emotional and psychological dimensions of family support. Households experiencing financial difficulties or other sources of strain may have less capacity to offer the necessary emotional assistance that is vital for the academic achievement of students (Conger et al., 2021). Parents who work several jobs or face financial instability may have limited time and energy to provide support or have meaningful discussions regarding their children's academic development. Students may experience feelings of isolation and reduced motivation in the absence of emotional support, particularly when they are already grappling with the challenges of higher education (Kuo et al., 2020).

Socioeconomic class also influences the level of academic support families provide. Research shows a correlation between parental involvement in school and improved academic performance, as well as a higher likelihood of pursuing post-secondary education (Hill & Tyson, 2021). Nevertheless, families hailing from lower socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds may encounter obstacles when it comes to engagement, such as language challenges, limited knowledge about the educational system, or conflicting obligations that consume their time (Cooper & Crosnoe, 2020). These obstacles can restrict their capacity to successfully assist their children in their education, perhaps resulting in lower academic performance and a decreased likelihood of achieving higher education.

Cultural influences and familial assistance

Cultural considerations, alongside socioeconomic position, exert a substantial influence on the nature and scope of family support in higher education. Cultural norms and expectations can influence families' perspectives and involvement in education, as well as the forms of assistance they provide to their children. For instance, several cultures place significant importance on the collective success of the family, perceiving the accomplishments of one family member as indicative of the honor and social standing of the entire family (González et al., 2019). Under such circumstances, families may have a higher propensity to allocate resources towards their children's education, even if it entails substantial personal or financial hardship.

In contrast, certain cultural contexts may prioritize urgent economic survival over long-term educational objectives, leading to a reduced focus on formal education. These disparities can result in variations in the amount of assistance given by families, as well as the demands placed on pupils in terms of their academic achievements (Chao & Kanatsu, 2020). Gaining insight into these cultural variables is essential for cultivating a full understanding of how familial assistance impacts higher education achievement.

Educational policy refers to the set of principles and guidelines that govern the educational system. It encompasses the rules and regulations that shape the curriculum, teaching methods, and overall structure of schools. Family support, on the other hand, refers to the assistance and resources provided to families in order to encourage their children's educational success.

The variations in family support among different socioeconomic and cultural origins have substantial consequences for educational policy. To ensure equitable access to academic support for all students in higher education, a comprehensive strategy is necessary to cater to the varying demands of families from diverse backgrounds. Educational institutions can effectively mitigate the disparity by offering supplementary assistance services, such as monetary assistance, educational guidance, and psychological support, specifically targeting students from socioeconomically disadvantaged households (Gaddis, 2019). Furthermore, implementing policies that encourage family involvement and engagement in education might enhance the support networks that are crucial for student achievement (Hill & Tyson, 2021).

Socioeconomic and cultural factors profoundly shape the intricate and diverse impact of family support on achieving higher education. Students from higher socioeconomic origins typically receive greater financial, emotional, and intellectual assistance, whereas those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds encounter severe obstacles that impede their educational achievements. To address these inequalities, we need a comprehensive strategy that considers the diverse needs of students and their families, prioritizing equal opportunities for all students to thrive in higher education.

3. Methodology

Research on the Causal Relationship Model of Factors Affecting High-Performance Schools under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast Region

The researcher conducted the study in 3 phases as follows:

Phase 1: Study of the Components of High-Performance Schools and Factors Affecting High-Performance Schools

1.1 Information Providers

For this research, the researcher divided the participants into 2 groups: one group for interviews and one group for evaluating the suitability and feasibility. Details for each group are as follows:

1.1.1 Experts: 5 individuals selected through purposive sampling for interviews concerning the components of high-performance schools and the factors affecting high-performance schools.

1.1.2 Experts: 5 individuals selected through purposive sampling to assess the suitability and feasibility of the components and factors affecting high-performance schools.

1.2 Variables Studied

1.2.1 Components of High-Performance Schools: The six components are: - Focus on Personnel Quality - Focus on Customers and Stakeholders - Organizational Leadership - Strategic Management - Organizational Culture - Organizational Innovation

1.2.2 Factors Affecting High-Performance Schools: For the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast region, the five factors are: - Change Leadership -

Human Resource Management - Organizational Member Competence - Total Quality Management - Learning Organization

Phase 2: Development and Verification of the Causal Relationship Model of Factors Affecting High-Performance Schools under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast Region

2.1 Population and Sample

2.1.1 Population: Includes school administrators and teachers under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast region for the academic year 2023, totaling 129,065 individuals, consisting of 12,098 school administrators and 116,967 teachers (Office of the Basic Education Commission, 2023, website).

2.1.2 Sample: Includes school administrators and teachers under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast region for the academic year 2023, totaling 600 individuals, consisting of 285 school administrators and 315 teachers. (The sample size was determined using a ratio of sample units to the number of variables of 20 to 1 (Nonglak Wiratchai, 1999). This study has 28 observable variables, so a minimum sample size of 560 was used. However, a sample of 600 was chosen, using multi-stage random sampling (Boonchom Srisawat, 2002)).

2.2 Variables Studied: The variables used in this research include causal variables and outcome variables as detailed below:

2.2.1 Causal Variables: Classified into 2 types:

2.2.1.1 Exogenous Variables: There is 1 variable, which is Change Leadership, measured by 5 observable variables: 1) Inspiring 2) Intellectual Stimulation 3) Building Prestige 4) Individual Consideration 5) Having Vision

2.2.1.2 Endogenous Variables: There are 4 variables: 1) Human Resource Management: Measured by 5 observable variables: - (1) Human Resource Management Strategy - (2) Recruitment - (3) Performance Evaluation - (4) Human Resource Development Planning - (5) Compensation and Benefits

2.2.2 Outcome Variable: High-Performance Schools, measured by 6 observable variables: - (1) Focus on Personnel Quality - (2) Focus on Customers and Stakeholders - (3) Organizational Leadership - (4) Strategic Management - (5) Organizational Culture - (6) Organizational Innovation

Phase 3: Exploring Approaches for Developing High-Performance Schools under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast Region

3.1 Information Providers

3.1.1 Experts: 5 individuals to evaluate the suitability, feasibility, and usefulness of approaches for developing high-performance schools.

3.2 Variables Studied

The approaches for developing factors affecting high-performance schools involve using variables that influence high-performance schools to create methods for developing schools into high-performance organizations.

Results

Research Findings on the Causal Relationship Model of Factors Affecting High-Performance Schools under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast Region

Summary of Findings:

1. Study of the Components of High-Performance Schools and Factors Affecting High Performance Schools

The components of high-performance schools include 6 aspects; focusing on personnel quality, focusing on customers and stakeholders, organizational leadership, strategic management, organizational culture, and organizational innovation. The evaluation of the suitability and feasibility of these components indicates that all components of high-performance schools are highly suitable and feasible overall.

The factors affecting high-performance schools include 5 factors; 1) Change Leadership, 2) Human Resource Management, 3) Learning Organization, 4) Total Quality Management, and 5) Organizational Member Competence. The evaluation of the suitability and feasibility of these factors shows that all factors affecting high-performance schools are highly suitable and feasible overall.

2. Development and Verification of the Causal Relationship Model of Factors Affecting High-Performance Schools under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast Region with Empirical Data

2.1 The Causal Relationship Model: The model of factors affecting high-performance schools under the Primary Education Service Area Office in the Northeast region is consistent with empirical data. The model fits well with the empirical data, with a Chi-square value of 340.30, degrees of freedom (df) of 309, a p-value of 0.11, a relative Chi-square value of 1.10, an RMSEA value of 0.01, a GFI value of 0.96, and an AGFI value of 0.95.

2.2 Relationships Between Variables: The relationship between Change Leadership, Human Resource Management, Learning Organization, Total Quality Management, and Organizational Member Competence affecting high-performance schools shows that; Direct Influence: Change Leadership has a significant positive direct effect on the high-performance schools variable, with an influence size of 0.93 at a statistical significance level of .01. Indirect Influence: Change Leadership has an indirect effect on the high-performance schools variable through the Learning Organization variable, with a significant statistical influence of .01 and an influence size of 0.45. It also has an indirect effect through the Organizational Member Competence variable, with a significant statistical influence of .05 and an influence size of 0.23. Total Influence: The high-performance schools variable is most influenced by Change Leadership, with a total influence size of 0.93, showing a

significant positive effect at a statistical significance level of .01. Structural Equation Model: The latent variables in the developed model can explain 95% of the variance in the high-performance schools variable, 92% of the variance in the Organizational Member Competence variable, 90% of the variance in the Total Quality Management variable, 90% of the variance in the Learning Organization variable, and 86% of the variance in the Human Resource Management variable, as illustrated in Figure 2.

*p < .05, **p < .01

Illustration of 2 models consistent with empirical data

3. A Study on the Development Approaches for Becoming a High-Performance Organization in Schools Under the Jurisdiction of Primary Educational Service Area Offices in Northeastern Thailand

The results of developing transformational leadership include aspects of inspiration, intellectual stimulation, charisma, individualized consideration, and vision. These factors contribute to schools under the jurisdiction of Primary Educational Service Area Offices in Northeastern Thailand becoming high-performance organizations. The approach to developing transformational leadership includes five areas, five objectives, five strategies, 53 methods of implementation, and 13 success indicators. The details are as follows:

3.1 Development of Inspiration: The objective is for administrators to inspire and motivate teachers and staff to learn, promote creativity to find new ways, and select methods for performing tasks. The strategy involves promoting inspiration in work performance. The evaluation of the suitability, feasibility, and benefits of developing inspiration shows that it is highly appropriate, feasible, and beneficial overall.

3.2 Development of Intellectual Stimulation: The objective is for school administrators to stimulate and motivate teachers and staff to create educational

innovations to achieve their goals. The strategy involves promoting a culture of learning and creativity in work practices through educational innovations. The evaluation of the suitability, feasibility, and benefits of developing intellectual stimulation shows that it is highly appropriate, feasible, and beneficial overall.

3.3 Development of Charisma: The objective is for school administrators to act as role models in knowledge, morality, ethics, and professional conduct. The strategy involves promoting the development of knowledge, morality, ethics, and professional ethics. The evaluation of the suitability, feasibility, and benefits of developing charisma shows that it is highly appropriate, feasible, and beneficial overall.

3.4 Development of Individualized Consideration: The objective is for school administrators to recognize individual differences among teachers and staff and assign tasks accordingly. The strategy involves promoting a caring and supportive management style. The evaluation of the suitability, feasibility, and benefits of developing individualized consideration shows that it is highly appropriate, feasible, and beneficial overall.

3.5 Development of Vision: The objective is for school administrators to implement processes that translate vision into action. The strategy involves promoting the creation and implementation of a vision. The evaluation of the suitability, feasibility, and benefits of developing vision shows that it is highly appropriate, feasible, and beneficial overall.

4. Discussions of Findings

From the research on the causal relationship model of factors influencing high-performance organizations in schools under the jurisdiction of Primary Educational Service Area Offices in Northeastern Thailand, the researcher discusses the research results as follows:

1. The Study of High-Performance Organization Components and Factors Influencing High-Performance Organizations in Schools

1.1 The study of the components of high-performance organizations in schools aimed at identifying these components found that high-performance organizations in schools consist of six components: focusing on personnel quality, focusing on service recipients and stakeholders, organizational leadership, strategic management, organizational culture, and organizational innovation. The research results emerged from the researcher's synthesis of documents, interviews with experts, and comprehensive evaluations of the suitability and feasibility of high-performance organization components in schools. The overall evaluation of the factors' suitability and feasibility was found to be at the highest level, reflecting that the school's operations, which include shared beliefs, values, and collaborative work behavior among teachers and staff, are integrated through mutual learning and implementation into effective work practices. Effective school management requires planning based on the analysis of past internal and external operations, seeking best practices, and integrating technology into management methods. These components align with the research of Sukanya Prom-arak (2021), who identified five components of high-performance organizations in schools: 1) the ability to produce high-performance outcomes, 2) systems, structures, and processes, 3) adaptability to change, 4)

decentralization, and 5) human resources. This is also consistent with Jatuporn Ngamsanguan and Supattana Kombupha (2017), who identified nine components of high-performance organizations in schools: 1) future vision, 2) strategic planning, 3) process and resource management, 4) personnel and team support, 5) student welfare, 6) stakeholder care, 7) knowledge management, 8) pursuit of academic excellence, and 9) sustaining success outcomes.

1.2 The study of factors influencing high-performance organizations in schools aimed at identifying these factors found five influencing factors: the learning organization, human resource management, organizational member competency, transformational leadership, and total quality management. The research results emerged from the researcher's synthesis of documents, interviews with experts, and comprehensive evaluations of the suitability and feasibility of factors influencing high-performance organizations in schools. The overall evaluation of the factors' suitability and feasibility was found to be at the highest level, reflecting that the school administrators' approach to managing with a focus on total quality is a management method that ensures quality in all aspects. This is achieved through the continuous participation of all parties in the development and improvement of quality to meet educational goals. The knowledge, skills, personality, and specific behavioral characteristics that teachers and school staff exhibit in their assigned duties contribute to the effective achievement of objectives. This aligns with Petcharat Jinnupong (2023), who stated that organizational members' competency is a factor that enhances an organization's competitiveness, particularly in human resource management, as competency is a factor that helps develop personnel potential, directly impacting organizational development. This is also consistent with Tosom Woraprawat and Jitima Wannasri (2023, p. 2805), who stated that developing schools into learning organizations leads to systematic knowledge management within the organization and creates a learning atmosphere in the school, supporting teachers and staff in continuous self-development and work improvement, which in turn enhances the quality of student learning.

2. Development and Verification of the Causal Relationship Model of Factors Affecting High-Performance Organizations in Schools Under the Office of the Basic Education Commission in the Northeastern Region with Empirical Data

The causal relationship model of factors affecting high-performance organizations in schools under the Office of the Basic Education Commission in the Northeastern region, as developed by the researcher, aligns with empirical data. The model includes an external latent variable, which is transformational leadership, and five internal latent variables: human resource management, learning organization, total quality management, organizational member competency, and high-performance organization in schools. The findings stem from a thorough review of related documents and research over the past 10 years, which were used to create the initial research framework. The content was synthesized at every stage, including the components, operational definitions, and behavioral indicators, and was preliminarily reviewed by the thesis advisor before being formulated into an interview guide for interviews with five experts. After creating the questionnaire, it was validated by experts, and the wording was refined. The questionnaire was tested, showing high reliability, and when the structural validity of the developed model was examined, it was found to align with empirical data. This is one reason why the causal

relationship model of factors affecting high-performance organizations in schools in the Northeastern region aligns with empirical data. Although the model was adjusted, this was to improve statistical appropriateness. The research findings correspond with various theories and concepts, as detailed below:

2.1 Direct Influence: It was found that transformational leadership has a direct positive influence on high-performance organizations in schools, with statistical significance at the .01 level. This indicates that transformational leadership is a critical characteristic of school administrators who can manage schools to respond to the current changes in education. School administrators who continually develop themselves and create administrative innovations, promoting teachers and staff to develop work practices and learning activities into educational innovations, play a vital role. Additionally, primary school administrators who foster a positive working atmosphere, facilitate continuous knowledge exchange, supervise diverse work operations, and incorporate technology into school management are more effective in handling changes. Therefore, transformational leadership is a direct influence on high-performance organizations in schools. This is consistent with Sunisa Thipat (2020), who found that transformational leadership has a positive direct influence on high-performance organizations, with an influence size of 0.03, statistically significant at the .01 level. It also aligns with Watcharapol Phophoonsak (2021, p. 66), who found that transformational leadership significantly impacts high-performance organizations at the .05 level. Similarly, Natchanuch Sudchadee, Thanomwan Prasitjaroensuk, and Songsak Phoosi-on (2018) found that transformational leadership directly influences high-performance organizations, with an influence size of 0.39.

2.2 Indirect Influence: It was found that the transformational leadership variable indirectly influences the high-performance organization variable in schools through the learning organization variable, with a positive influence and statistical significance at the .01 level. This might be because transformational leadership is a theory that can broadly explain the influence process, from micro-level interactions between leaders and individual followers to the entire organizational system. The primary role of transformational leadership is to initiate various changes within the organization. A management approach that leads to organizational success involves creating a learning organization, characterized by an environment that fosters learning, a culture that instills collective knowledge creation, and school administrators who support and promote collaborative learning within the organization. They develop teachers and staff to gain knowledge and expertise, encourage the application of knowledge in work, and create a place where new ideas emerge, where everyone is inspired and learns together in developing the school. By supporting continuous learning readiness among all personnel, administrators can ensure that the organization is prepared for change and can promote sustainable development, directly contributing to the school's status as a high-performance organization. This is consistent with Surasak Chamaram (2019), who found that transformational leadership indirectly influences high-performance organizations through organizational culture. It also aligns with Nisara Hongsa (2017), who found that leadership factors affecting high-performance organizations include supporting organizational culture, strategic direction, and organizational balance, collectively explaining 56.50% of the variance, with statistical significance at the .05 level.

The transformational leadership variable also has an indirect effect through the organizational member competency variable, with a positive influence and statistical significance at the .01 level. This might be because transformational leadership involves the leader's influence or power to persuade subordinates to perform their duties effectively, achieving the school's goals. It is a trait of administrators that promotes the competency of organizational members in schools, enabling them to cope with global changes. School administrators must plan efficiently and harness the potential of each school member to work creatively. This means that teachers' and staff's knowledge and abilities in schools must keep pace with technology and contribute to educational advancement. Effective educational management requires transformational leadership with vision, empowerment, and the ability to motivate. Enhancing and developing the competencies of members in schools can increase the school's potential or promote it as a high-performance organization. This is consistent with Pirallarat Rungsai and Saranee Usenyang (2022), who stated that organizational member competency is an individual or task-specific characteristic that drives the achievement of organizational goals. It is crucial for staff to possess knowledge of their duties, work accurately, solve problems efficiently, and achieve goals effectively.

2.3 Total Influence: It was found that the high-performance organization variable in schools is most influenced by the transformational leadership variable, with a positive influence and statistical significance at the .01 level. This might be because transformational leadership can manage schools efficiently and meet school objectives through appropriate processes. Transformational leaders who recognize and prioritize the correct methods of internal and external organizational change have a systematic approach to operations and instill a sense of responsibility in subordinates, leading to effective goal-oriented behavior. Moreover, they create and promote factors that contribute to high-performance organizations in schools, such as fostering a learning organization with channels for knowledge sharing among personnel, coupled with continuous and diverse external knowledge acquisition. Prioritizing the learning organization in developing the institution is essential, as it helps build a strong knowledge base to keep pace with the constant changes in global society. This is consistent with Natchanuch Sudchadee (2018, p. 67), who found that transformational leadership has a total influence on high-performance organizations, with an influence size of 0.65, positively significant at the .01 level.

3. A Study on Approaches to Developing High-Performance Organizations in Schools Under the Office of the Primary Educational Service Area in Northeastern Thailand

The development approaches for transformational leadership include five aspects: inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, idealized influence, individualized consideration, and having a clear vision. These aspects contribute to the development of high-performance organizations in schools under the Office of the Primary Educational Service Area in Northeastern Thailand. The development of transformational leadership in these five aspects has been found to be appropriate, feasible, and beneficial at the highest level in all areas. This is because school administrators place importance on the individual differences among teachers and staff, assigning tasks according to their suitability. The administration based on the principles of "Kalyanamitta" (good friendship) by school

administrators shows a correlational relationship. If the administration based on Kalyanamitta principles increases, the results of school management tend to improve; conversely, if it decreases, school management results tend to decline. This finding aligns with Phawana Kittivimonchai and Saowanee Sirisuksilp (2016), who proposed seven approaches to building high-performance organizations in schools, including enhancing the potential of human resources, managing information and communication technology, designing and improving processes, focusing on service recipients, fostering innovation, emphasizing outcomes, and creating a learning organization

5. Recommendations

1. Recommendations for Applying the Research Findings

1.1 The research findings indicate that the components of a high-performance organization in schools consist of six elements: focusing on personnel quality, focusing on service recipients and stakeholders, organizational leadership, strategic management, organizational culture, and organizational innovation. Therefore, the Office of the Primary Educational Service Area in Northeastern Thailand can use these components as a framework for assessing the performance of schools as high-performance organizations.

1.2 The research findings show that transformational leadership, which includes inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, idealized influence, individualized consideration, and having a clear vision, has both direct and indirect influences on schools becoming high-performance organizations. Therefore, school administrators need to prioritize and act as transformational leaders, particularly as academic leaders who seek knowledge, develop skills, and explore management models that align with global changes. They should instill motivation in teachers and staff to perform their duties, encourage continuous self-development, and set an example in knowledge, morality, ethics, discipline, and professional conduct. This will establish charismatic leadership, earning respect and faith from teachers and staff, who can then follow the example set for them. Moreover, leaders should have a broad vision and allow teachers and staff to participate in analyzing, designing, setting methods of practice, and determining success indicators in a systematic manner to ensure that goals are met accurately, quickly, and efficiently.

1.3 The research findings reveal that the approaches to developing transformational leadership are highly appropriate, feasible, and beneficial. Therefore, primary schools and the Office of the Primary Educational Service Area can develop transformational leadership, which will promote the formation of high-performance organizations in schools by following these developmental approaches.

2. Recommendations for Future Research

2.1 Future research should explore other factors, such as human resource management, learning organizations, total quality management, and organizational member competencies, to understand why they do not influence schools becoming high-performance organizations.

2.2 Research should also investigate other factors not studied in this research, such as innovative leadership, information technology, organizational commitment, and other factors that may influence schools becoming high-performance organizations under the Office of the Primary Educational Service Area in Northeastern Thailand. The findings can then be used as guidelines for developing high-performance organizations in schools within the Office of the Primary Educational Service Area in Northeastern Thailand.

2.3 This topic should be studied using other research methodologies, such as Participatory Action Research (PAR), Research and Development (R&D), or Grounded Theory, to compare, confirm, or further develop the findings of this research.

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